

The effects of industrial production, inflow remittances, and FDI on the rate of Inflation in Liberia 2000-2020

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Abstract:

The effects of industrial production, inflow remittance, and FDI on the rate of inflation is the title of the research. The case study is Liberia and the analysis was tested through the Johansen co-integration and the correction miscalculation/ error model (ECM) was instigated. And both tools were used to establish the long-run relationship between the research variables. The testing of various research parameters presumed that there exists a long-run interaction between inflow remittances, FDI, and Inflation but realized that industrial production and inflation have a negative response to each other (an increase in production decreases inflation and vice versa). The Liberian government can prioritize the improvement in industrial production in the manufacturing sector which will reduce the rate of inflation. Furthermore, FDI and inflow remittance can be monitor and encourage foreign investors to invest which will decrease unemployment and the inflow of new technologies in all sectors. When these suggestions are followed strategically, this could decrease the rate of inflation and help citizens improve their lives.

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I. Introduction

Globally, inflation has declined over the past five decades with national consumer price inflation down from a peak of nearly in 1974 to a low in 2019. These ecstatic results can be attributed to the stabilization of output, workforce, and increase in growth output and investment leading to higher openness in the prices of commodities, creating vibrant investors with long-term objectives, etc. Liberia as a small open economy depends mostly on imported commodities as well as remittances from citizens abroad, who sometimes invest in a business and also support the high consumption rate from the perspective of the household.

One of the macroeconomic problems in Liberia has been inflation especially in 2002 -2018, World Bank, 2020. Liberia as an imported-based economy has been faced with the turmoil of high inflation, which is influence by poor infrastructure, low production capacity by firms, and the government's inability to pay back her public debt. Also, the changes of money from 1985-1990, 1998-2003, 2011 -2020 has been the mean contributing factor to the high inflation rate in Liberia. Interestingly, the current administration is presenting the argument of changing the currency to another denomination this year. According to the Central bank of Liberia, reports says that the reason behind this is to know the total currency in circulation.

In Liberia, it is observed that industrial production is going down the ladder because of the lack of profits seen by producer, which only signifies that inflation is at a higher peak, with that inflows of remittances has a two-way direction which includes income from the host and home countries that determines the correlation of positive and negative implication on the inflows of remitted money in the home country. (Barua, 2011) indicated that higher inflation affects individual remittances and (Salisu et.al, 2001) postulated that FDI eases the negative effect of inflation on an economy. This means that investments from investors should be one of the tools that government should instigate in minimizing inflation in their economy.

The aim is to reveal that there is a long-run relationship between industrial production, FDI, inflow remittances, and the rate of inflation, in applying the data, the selection of time series from 2000 to 2020 is perfect for the evaluation process. So, in a specific connotation, this research will measure out the effect of FDI, industrial production, and inflow remittances on the rate of inflation. The structure of the research is in the following algorithm. Part two comprises the review of various similar literature. Part three reveals the methodological connotation in detail; few specifications of the formulated model and data were included. Part four gives vivid results on the empirical and findings interpretation. Of course, the concluding statements and policy recommendations are composed of part five.

II. The review of the works of literature

The current and past decades have produced sufficient empirical studies on inflation, linking it with a variety of other variables for quantitative testing in specific models. Several of the variables that were involved in the researches were exchange rate, increase in countries population, trade openness, personal and general remittances, commodities, bonds, etc. all of these variables have some level of link up with inflation. These variables were conducted in different countries yielding different results that provided diverse policy recommendations. Interestingly, the variables used in this research have not been empirically tested in Liberia, especially in the past and current decades. The next paragraphs below signify some of the studies conducted in different countries with similar variables.

The empirical study (Bibi et al., 2014) indicated that both FDI and trade openness should be referred to as pivotal ingredients that improve the level of impact economic growth has on the

population and examine a long-run relationship among the openness of trade, FDI, imports, exports, and exchange rate. Regarding substantial input on the research and (Gokmenoglu et al., 2015) entrench that there exists a long-run relationship among these variables(industrial production, FDI, GDP, and the prices of oil in specific environment) and when tested, it reveals to us that the oil price to industrial production move in the same direction.

Tochukwu et al. (2018) elaborated through an investigated study that provided a relationship between inflation and industrial output. Evidence from this study suggests to us an insignificant and positive relationship between the parameters of research. Unstable inflation creates a corridor for an industrial output gap which proves that there should be an authentic forecasting process in mitigating the rate of inflation. A proposed study by Xinying et al.(2019) investigated that inflow remittances and total exporting of commodities have a significant and direct impact on the growth of an economy and FDI is only positive when it is an individual factor specifically in west Africa, also Meyer et.al (2017) acknowledged the phenomenon based on 6 high remittances receiving countries stating that the relationship between the two variables is positively highlighting a favorable GDP. Inflow remittance inflow is a major indicating factor in underdeveloped countries especially in Liberia, continuous research on FDI and remittance postulated that both factors have a direct significant effect on per capita income (Anwar et.al, 2015), exchange rates (Sinha et al., 2019).

From the review of the literature, the understanding suggests that FDI, industrial production, and inflow remittances all have an effect (positive and negative) on inflation and also vice versa. The literature also provides that other macroeconomics variables can impact inflation over a specific time interval. In summary, there has been researched on these variables but all have been individually tested. So, this study will use this existing knowledge to combine all of them and give suggestions for a long and short term that could be used in underdeveloped and developing economies.

III. Data and methodology

A. Data

This study analyzes the perennial time series of 2000 to 2020 in Liberia. The presented data collected in this research involve the consideration for Inflation (yearly), foreign direct investment (inflows, currency US\$), Industrial production (export % in rubber), and inflows remittances (currency US\$). The data we consider were taken from the Ministry of Finance, World Bank Indicators on parameters, and the Central Bank of Liberia.

B. Methodology

We employ the stationarity test which initially provided the integrating of every variable in the research. The conduction of the first process and all variables have been stationary into the second difference. The evaluation took the trend on the co-integration analysis and ECM which have a display that there is indeed a long-run effect relationship between variables. Results also have a display that some of the independent variables are affecting the dependent variable in a direction of positivity.

a. Specifying the Model formulated

GDP (Inflation) $t = f$ (industrial production, FDI, inflow remittances)

(1) Or we can display as $Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3\dots)$

The transformational outcome has the following form:

$\text{Log (GDP (inflation))}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log (\text{industrial production})_t + \beta_2 \log (\text{inflow remittance})_t + \beta_3 \log (\text{Foreign direct investment})_t + \mu t$ (2) $\text{Log (Y)}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log(X_1)_t + \beta_2 \log(X_2)_t + \beta_3 \log(X_3)_t + \mu t$

In this explanation;

Y: rate of inflation is suggested in terms of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

X_{1t} : industrial production in time value t

X_{2t} : FDI in time value t

X_{3t} : Inflow remittances in time value t

β_0 = Intercept.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ and β_4 = the coefficient of regression.

μ_t = term of the error t.

IV. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

This study begins with the analysis by testing for the availability of unit root using augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Philips-Perron tests (PP).

A. Test for Unit Root: Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philips-Peron Test

In conducting unit root test, the hypothesis is:

H1: There is a unit root

The actuality of all of the listed testing tools is diverse techniques to investigate or evaluate the availability of stationarity in the data collected ADF test, PP test, Dicker Fuller GLS (ERS) test, Kwiatkowski Philipps-Schin-shin test, Elliot-Rothenberg-Stock point optimal test, Ng-Perron test, etc.)... For the sake of this research, the author decided to stay with the ADF test and PP test because they are best for every evaluation process especially in the case of the research case country, and the ADF test is valid in colossal samples the regression linearity authenticates the issue of serial correlation. To approve the ADF test, the PP test was conducted especially.

Table 1: Stationary test at each selected level

Parameters	ADF		Test of PP		Conclusion
	Statistic Test	Prob.	Test statistic	Prob.	
Inflation(GDP)	-0.343475	0.9825	1.194974	0.9344	Non-stationary
FDI	-1.606299	0.1001	-1.571441	0.1068	Non-stationary
inflow remittance	-0.323276	0.5528	-0.362741	0.5377	Non-stationary
Industrial production	0.000871	0.6711	0.000871	0.6711	Non-stationary

Source: Calculations using Eview

An exploration of the parameters using ADF and PP tests reveals that all parameters Y (Inflation, expressed in GDP), X_1 : industrial production, X_2 : inflows remittances, and X_3 : FDI have no stationary in the level, i.e. at I (0). Consequently, the stationarity test of those parameters in the second difference at all levels (1%, 5%, and 10%), (table 1). In that view, the need to evaluate a stationarity test at the second difference is inevitable.

Table 2: At Second Difference Test

Parameters	ADF		PP Test		Conclusion
	Statistic Test	Probab	Statistical Test	Probab	
Inflation(GDP)	-5.956882	0.0000	-6.135132	0.0000	Stationary
FDI	-8.071612	0.0000	-16.87496	0.0001	Stationary
Inflow remittance	-4.111790	0.0007	-6.204151	0.0000	Stationary
Industrial production	-4.565263	0.0001	-7.796617	0.0000	Stationary

Source: Calculation using Eview

The observational results in table 2 portray that all tested parameters are stationary after the 2nd difference I (2) at all levels (1%, 5%, and 10%). After that, the next step is the test of Cointegration.

B. The Criteria of Var Lag

The provision submits that the structure of integration of the evaluated series is in the 2nd differences level, to establish the co-integration between those parameters. Nevertheless, to finish this, the application of the VAR Lag order selection criteria method is required. So the above table establishes the criteria of VAR lag.

Table 3: The Order Criteria in the VAR lag testing

Lag	Log L	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-926.8261	NA	6.62E+52	132.9752	133.1577	132.9583
1	-881.3339	58.48991	1.12E+51	128.762	129.6749	128.6775
2	-829.5854	36.96325*	1.55e+49*	123.6551*	125.2983*	123.5029*
0	-926.8261	NA	6.62E+52	132.9752	133.1577	132.9583

Source: Calculated using E-views.

Most times, the higher lags are established by agreeing with the values in AIC or SC with a condition of the less the value of criteria, the plausible the results ($123.6551^* < 125.2983^*$) i.e. AIC.

A. The Test of Johansen

To evaluate a test of Johansen, the established hypothesis says:

H1: There is co-integration among variables,

Table 4: Evaluation of Cointegration

Test of the rank of Cointegration				
Hypothesis	Trace Value		Level of 0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistical test	C. Value	Prob.
None *	0.996781	133.7348	47.85613	0
At most 1 *	0.919587	53.39378	29.79707	0
At most 2 *	0.612801	18.1056	15.49471	0.0198
At most 3 *	0.291383	4.822156	3.841466	0.0281

Source: calculation using E-views.

Test of the rank of cointegration (Less value Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesis		Max-Eigen	Level 0.05	
Value in CE	Eigenvalue	Statistic	C. Value	Prob.
None *	0.996781	80.34105	27.58434	0
At most 1 *	0.919587	35.28817	21.13162	0.0003
At most 2	0.612801	13.28345	14.2646	0.071
At most 3 *	0.291383	4.822156	3.841466	0.0281

Source: Calculation using E-views

Calculations in Table 4, showed only the higher-eigenvalue which indicates the appearance of one cointegrating equation at a 5% level of significance. Three of the parameters in the calculation poses to have a long-run equilibrium relationship among their interactions but industrial production and inflation have a negative relationship.

IV. ESTIMATION OF THE LONG-RUN EQUATION

With the establishment that there is a long-run relationship between the parameters, this research also provides that there is linearity, none heteroscedasticity and also there is no stability among the parameters.

Table 5: Evaluating the Long-run Equation

Parameters	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
X ₃	-3570232.	0.2938990	-1.214782	0.2478
X ₂	2.002891	0.454495	3.052227	0.0100
X ₁	2.385134	-1.007729	2.366840	0.0356
C	1.10E+09	1.84E+08	5.982122	0.0001
R-squared	0.869944	Mean dependent var	2.33E+09	
Adjusted R-squared	0.837429	S.D. dependent var	9.11E+08	
S.E. of regression	3.67E+08	Akaike info criterion	42.49348	
Sum squared resid	1.62E+18	Schwarz criterion	42.68663	
Log-likelihood	-335.9479	Hannan-Quinn criteria.	42.50337	
F-statistic	26.75587	Durbin-Watson stat		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000013			

Source: Calculations using E-views

From the look of thing Table, 5 indicates there is a long-run interaction of Inflation (Y), industrial production (X₁), inflows remittance (X₂), and FDI inflows(X₃). From all plausible observations, the existing results pinpoint the equation as:

$$Y = 1.10E+09 + 2.385134 * X_1 + 2.302891 * X_2 + 3570232.00 * X_3$$

VII. LONG-RUN EQUATION DISCUSSION

Table 5 provides an overview of the various numbers that were gathered during the test. It can be used to interpret the results.

a. R-Squared (R²)

(Maddala and Kajal, 2009) discussed the importance of R² in model data. R² is the sum of the various factors that affect the dependent variable's variation. It shows that the main contributors to the variation are the various regressors.

b. F-statistic

This finding shows that the probability of F-statistic is less than or equal to the P-value. It also shows that the regression model is significant at a level of 5%.

c. Industrial production (X₁)

The statistical significance of industrial production is also statistically significant. This coefficient has a higher p-value relative to the critical value.

d. Inflow remittance

The long-run results indicate that the inflow remittance has a positive p-value of 0.554495. This indicates that a 1% increase leads to a 0.554495% increase in the level of inflation.

e. Foreign Direct investment

(Umeora, 2013) researched that FDI decreases the GDP growth in a developing country, moreover the rate of inflation move to a higher figure and has a bi-directional effect on the exchange rate in Nigeria. The long-run equation shows that the inflow remittance coefficient is -3570232 and it has a smaller p-value than the critical value. This means that an increase in FDI leads to a higher inflation level.

d. Constant value

The constant value of the Y-intercept is a proof of the correctness of the model. It shows that the model's predictions are consistent with the statistical significance of the constant value.

VIII. ESTIMATION OF THE SHORT-RUN MODEL

The following algorithms are used in estimating the error correction model. It shows that the model returns to equilibrium after the variable's shift in its orientation.

Table 6: Miscalculation Correction Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.08E+08	38816517	2.782234	0.0194
D(X)	1.066039	0.453220	2.352144	0.0405
D(X01)	0.551323	0.338582	1.628328	0.1345
D(X02)	598367.1	1388350.	0.430992	0.6756
RESID01(-1)	-0.262111	0.130306	-2.011501	0.0720
R-squared	0.490184	Mean dependent var	1.45E+08	
Adjusted R-squared	0.286258	S.D. dependent var	1.69E+08	
S.E. of regression	1.43E+08	Akaike info criterion	40.65131	
Sum squared resid	2.04E+17	Schwarz criterion	40.88732	
Log-likelihood	-299.8848	Hannan-Quinn criteria	40.64879	
F-statistic	2.403730	Durbin-Watson stat	1.627503	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.118851			

Source: Calculations using E-views

The error correction coefficient is a negative and statistically significant measure. It shows that 26% of the disequilibrium among variables can be corrected in one year.

IX. DIAGNOSTIC TESTS

The diagnostic test is used to determine if the economic model is operating according to plan. It is an absolute determination if the model's estimators are not blue.

A. Test of heteroscedasticity

For the heteroskedasticity test, the hypothesis is:

H1: Existence of heteroscedasticity.

Below table 7 presents the results of the heteroscedasticity test.

Table 7. Heteroscedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.191620	Prob. F(4,10)	0.9373
Obs*R-squared	1.067869	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.8993
Scaled explained SS	0.212685	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.9947

Source: Calculations using E-views

In table 7, we can see that the Obs*R-cubic 1.06 is higher than the threshold of significance or 10%.

A. Test of serial Correlation

In conducting a serial correlation test, the hypothesis is:

H0: There is no serial correlation.

Table 8. B/G Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	0.058342	Prob. F(1,9)	0.8145
Obs*R-squared	0.096611	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.7559

Source: Calculations in E-views

Given Table 8, as well as Obs*R-squared 0.096611, is higher than the 10% level of significance, so H0 is accepted and rejects H1, that there is no serial correlation.

A. Test for Autocorrelation (Correlogram-Q-Statistic)

The autocorrelation gives a vivid picture of the correlation between values of the process at different times or intervals. It occurs when the error value at different times is positively correlated.

In conducting a test of autocorrelation the hypothesis is:

H0: no autocorrelation of errors,

Table 9: Correlogram Test for Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob*
. .	. .	1	0.060	0.060	0.06650.797
. .	. .	2	-0.025	-0.029	0.07860.961
. .	. .	3	0.052	0.056	0.13630.987
. * .	. * .	4	-0.075	-0.083	0.26620.992
. *	. *	5	0.078	0.092	0.42000.995
. ** .	. ** .	6	-0.239	-0.266	2.04420.916
. * .	. * .	7	-0.129	-0.077	2.57190.922
. * .	. ** .	8	-0.205	-0.252	4.09990.848
. .	. *	9	0.035	0.122	4.15300.901
. * .	. ** .	10	-0.101	-0.223	4.66950.912
. ** .	. * .	11	-0.243	-0.162	8.44650.673
. .	. * .	12	0.019	-0.116	8.47680.747

Source: Calculation using E-views

The above results of table 9 show, the possibilities are bigger numbers than a 10% level of importance up to 12th Lag, this simply implies that the 0 hypothesis is true and the other hypothesis is ignored. With that, the researcher proclaimed that there exists no autocorrelation of errors at diverse times.

A. Stability Test

To conduct the test of stability, the hypothesis is:

H0: Agreement of stability,

Figure 1: Test of existence in CUSUM

Source: Calculation using Eview

A. Misspecification Test

The conduction of this test, reveals the selected hypothesis of:

H0: It was specified,

Whenever there is the process of collecting data, some data are inevitable and can be exempted, or in the creation of the model, the incorrect theory can be submitted. It can be wrong parameters and providing false results. Then, the specified model to have proven accurate results.

Table 10: Ramsey Possibility Test

	Value	df	Probability
T-statistic	0.981345	9	0.3521
F-statistic	0.963038	(1, 9)	0.3521
Likelihood ratio	1.524863	1	0.2169

Source: Calculations using Eview

The calculation reveals results that the provided possibilities of Log-possibilities ratio 0.2169 or approximately 21% are bigger in number than 10%. So then the forecasted H0 is agreed; see table 10

G. Normality Test

In conducting a test of normality, the hypothesis is that:

The test of normality, suggest a hypothesis which states:

H0: The residuals are normally distributed,

Table 11: Test of Normality

Model	
J.Bera Stat	1.516910
Prob.	0.468389

Source: Calculations using Eview

The answers we gathered from table 11 showed that J.Bera Probability 0.468389 approximately 47% is greater than the 10% level of importance means that it is canceled, then

it is affirmed that they are normally distributed. The submitted results suggest that the modular suggestion is applicable to be used by Liberia's policymakers.

X. Conclusion and Recommendation

The researcher formulated the concluding part of the research by explaining each variable as it affects the rate of inflation. The variables each have a degree of effect on the growth of the Liberian economy because all of them influence the growth of citizens in all sectors that employ workers (skilled or unskilled). Therefore below are the explanations of each tested variable and its impact.

A. Inflow remittances Received-suggested policy implications and recommendations

This article has informed readers/students and policymakers that the inflows of remittances have a great deal of positivity and have a long-run effect on Liberia's inflation rate and vice versa. It suggests that an increase in the population's purchasing power will directly lead to more consumption and therefore this effect will lead to an increase in inflation. In Liberia, policies should be taken to manage remittances inflow from consumption intentions to invest in sectors that are productive which causes economic growth. In that light, the financial institutions can support in diversifying inflow remittances into productive investment opportunities for example financial market and innovative capacity building. Furthermore, there is minute support by remittances towards the rate of inflation compared to the other significant variables of the model. Thus, the inflationary effect originating from remittance inflows can be normalized by promoting GDP growth and ensuring the flows of remittances in productive latent sectors.

B. Industrial production – suggested policy implication and recommendations

In the research, the result can be explained with the accession that industrial production and inflation have a negative relationship. This means that an increase at a certain level of industrial production directly decreases inflation and vice versa. Liberia should prioritize the development of manufacturing in all of its productive sectors which gives producers the knowledge of emphasizing potential commodities. That being said, policymakers should consider the rate of inflation when attempting to prognoses changes in the output gap, nevertheless, in the long run, unstable inflation can contribute to the industrial output of commodities, therefore inflation needs to be observed consistently.

C. Foreign Direct Investment: suggested policy implication and recommendations

It was seen in results that FDI and inflation have a positive relationship at every increase or decrease in each level. Also, Though FDI provides the existences of development, increase employment level of the population and increase investments in the various sector yet the result can be explained by the idea that FDI increases inflation rate in Liberia. Findings from the research indicate that FDI in latent developing sectors in an economy like Liberia minimizes/ reduces the negative effect that inflation will spread out to the entire nation. The government of Liberia should load more efforts on FDI as it will help stabilize the inflation rate over the periods to come even though we are faced will problems like Covid 19 and the major element called the exchange rate.

Additionally, inflows remittances and industrial production have very minute contributions towards inflation. The other parameter (FDI) strongly contributes to larger figures. In fact, the reactions of inflation emanating from inflows remittance can be suppressed by improving the growth of GDP. Onwards, the circulation of inflows remittances in potential sectors is

imperative for the Liberia case study. Finally, to conclude, there is no doubt that the impact of FDI and inflows of money to the increase in the rate of inflation in the long run in Liberia but according to the tested result, industrial production and inflation have a negative relationship. So in this view, the government should turn a look view into the variables selected in this research topic during the procedure of developmental policy and the process of implementing them.

References

- Anwar, S., & Cooray, A. (2015). Financial flows and per capita income in developing countries. *International Review of Economics and Finance*, 35, 304–314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2014.10.009>
- Barua, S. (2011). Determinants of Workers' Remittances in Bangladesh: An Empirical Study. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1398690>
- Bibi, S., Ahmad, S. T., & Rashid, H. (2014). Impact of Trade Openness, FDI, Exchange Rate and Inflation on Economic Growth: A Case Study of Pakistan. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 1(1), 236. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijafr.v4i2.6482>
- Gokmenoglu, K., Azin, V., & Taspinar, N. (2015). The Relationship between Industrial Production, GDP, Inflation and Oil Price: The Case of Turkey. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 25(May), 497–503. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(15\)00762-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(15)00762-5)
- Salisu, M., & Balasubramanyam, V. (2001). *Foreign direct investment and globalization*. 76(April 2004), 419–443. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203183410.ch9>
- Sinha, M., Tirtosuharto, D., & Sengupta, P. P. (2019). Impacts of FDI and Remittance Inflows in Developing Asia: A Comparative Dynamic Panel Study. *Economic Papers*, 38(4), 311–328. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1759-3441.12260>
- The World Bank (2019) IBRD.IDA. Print Publication Information. Retrieved September 3, 2021. <https://data.worldbank.org/country/liberia>
- Tochukwu, Okafor, C., Esther, Adegbite, O., Abiola, Babajide, A., & Emeka, U. (2018). Inflation dynamics and the industrial output gap in Nigeria. *International Review of Economics and Finance*, February, 419–430.
- Umeora, C. E. (2013). Effects of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2010, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2285329>
- Xinying, J., Oppong, S., & Vitenu-Sackey, P. A. (2019). Impact of Human Capital Development and Human Capital Isolation Mechanisms on Innovative Performance: Evidence from Industrial Companies in Jordan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 11(15), 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.7176/EJBM>

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